

Google Pixel 3 Setup documentation

Date of Setup: 7th May 2025

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Update.

Setup of phone was 20 April 2024. After looking for updates,
Still not offered a new browser, assistant when review configuration of phone.

Opening Chrome – Changing Search Engine.

New options to turn on privacy features.

Now is possible to change engine browser. Configuration > Settings > Search engine. The options available are Yahoo, Bing, Yandex, DuckDuckGo.

Trying to eliminate Chrome.

Trying to eliminate chrome selecting the app in home screen.

Not possible to eliminate. You can disable only after the message **“....you can't delete this app since it came pre-installed on your device, By disabling you turn this app off and hide in on your device”**.

After accepting google icon is not show anymore in phone.

Looking for more browsers.

In the App store Looking for Chrome after Disable it show the option to Enable, however for the other browser the option is on Install.

Safari browser (Apple) is not offered, is offered a similar browser

Looking “Browsers” shows the following options Opera, Brave, Browser for android, Samsung browser, Microsoft edge. (In that order)

Downloading other browsers.

I choose to download Microsoft Edge. After downloading the icon is shown in the home screen.

When Microsoft edge is open for the first time, It gives the option of change Edge as the default browser app (Within Microsoft edge app)

Using different Browser, search engine.

Going to configuration > Default apps we can see now Edge as the “Default Browser”

It is open Microsoft Edge; the search engine is by default Bing. we can change the search engine, with the same options as in Google chrome; Bing, Yahoo, Google, Yandex and DuckDuckGo

Downloading other browsers.

It's downloaded a third browser. "Mi Browser" by Zhigu corporation.

After installing and opening "Mi Browser" shows the option to add it as the default browser app and change the search engine.

Downloading other apps

It's downloaded Outlook Lite.

Not problems with the download and use.

Factory Reset

First: Basic Settings

No changes

Standard configuration
New design (Purple color)

Setup – Review „aditional“ apps

In case clicking „NO THANKS“ in Anything else. It will automatically download 8 applications Google Docs, Google Meet, Google Home, Google Keep.

To avoid this you should click in „Review additional apps“ and deselect the apps.

You can allow to customize your search with Google Assistant but its already downloaded

Setting up new Google Account

No differences

Setting up a new Google account – **Mandatory to start using cellphone** „create account“ (for personal use):

Name: Dice

Gender: Rather not say

Birthday: 25th April 2000

E-Mail: dicephoneproject2405@gmail.com

Password: Dice24.05

Home Screen- App downloaded

Home screen shows Chrome, Gmail, Google Maps as default and ready to use App.

In all setting process doesnt give any offer for other apps that are not google apps.

Google Chrome – Search Engine

When is open Google Chrome, you can change the Search Engine.

One difference is in the Browser offer, **Yandex is not offer anymore and now it is offer Ecosia**

9:51 G ↓

9:51 G ↓

9:51 G ↓

9:52 G ↓

9:53 G ↓

New tab

New tab

Search engine

consent.yahoo.com/v2/colle

Welcome to Chrome

By using Chrome, you agree to the [Google Terms of Service](#), and the [Google Chrome and Chrome OS Additional Terms of Service](#).

Help make Chrome better by sending usage statistics and crash reports to Google.

Accept & continue

Search or type web address

Search or type web address

Search engine

Google
google.com

Yahoo!
yahoo.com
Location and notifications are allowed

Bing
bing.com

DuckDuckGo
duckduckgo.com

Ecosia
ecosia.org

Suche

yahoo!

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App store – Downloading new Browser

As before it doesn't offer any Browser when its open App Store

Looking “Browsers” shows the following options Firefox, Duck Duck Go, Brave, Microsoft Edge, Opera. Random order compared with the order before Factory reset (Opera, Brave, Browser for android, Samsung browser, Microsoft edge)

Using different Browser, search engine.

I choose to download Microsoft Edge. After downloading the icon is shown in the home screen.

When Microsoft edge is open for the first time, It gives the option of change Edge as the default browser app (Within Microsoft edge app)

You can change the search engine as before.

Trying to eliminate Chrome.

Same as before the factory reset. Trying to eliminate chrome selecting the app in home screen is not possible

You can disable only after the message “.....you can't delete this app since it came pre-installed on your device, By disabling you turn this app off and hide in on your device”.

After accepting google icon is not show anymore in phone.

App store – Downloading new Browser

As before it doesn't offer any Browser when its open App Store

Looking “Browsers” shows the following options Opera, Brave, Ai Browser as Sponsored apps. Selecting know more about Sponsored apps you can see some information like Company, country of the browser that paid for the spot.

No differences within browsers to set up as default

Downloading other apps

It's downloaded Outlook Lite.

Not problems with the download and use.

Going into configuration of phone you can see the default apps. I change the default Browser, disable the Google Assistant (Non show anymore)

Principals' findings

Still necessary to create a Google Account to use the Phone

Google Chrome, Google, Google assistant, Google Maps are automatically downloaded.

In the set-up process you have the option to **deselect some** apps of Google; Docs, Meet, Home Keep to avoid they download automatically.

In the process of set up is not option to change the default browser, search engine, assistant.

To change the default browser, you need to go to app store, look for a browser, download the browser, open the browser and then you will have the option to choose it as default browser

In play store is random order in the browser search however exist “sponsored” browsers that are shown first.

The offer to change Search Engine are basically the same for all browser; Bing Yahoo, Google, DuckDuck GO, Yandex

You can't eliminate Google Chrome, Google and all other “default” Google apps you can only disable after clicking accept to the message “....**you can't delete this app since it came pre-installed on your device, By disabling you turn this app off and hide in on your device**”.